

Supporting Information:

Limitations of Quantum Hardware for Molecular Energy Estimation Using VQE

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S1 Effective Hamiltonian

To construct the effective Hamiltonian, we apply the frozen core approximation. In this approach, the molecular spin-orbitals are divided into three sets:

- **Core spin-orbitals:** low-energy spin-orbitals that are treated as an effective potential in the Hamiltonian;
- **Active spin-orbitals:** which are treated explicitly in the Hamiltonian;
- **Truncated spin-orbitals:** corresponding to high-energy spin-orbitals that are not included in the Hamiltonian.

In this work we used a spin-orbital basis, where spin-up (α) and spin-down (β) components are interleaved. In this basis the effective Hamiltonian is defined as

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{\text{eff}} = \sum_{pq}^{\text{act}} \tilde{h}_{pq} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_q + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{pqrs}^{\text{act}} g_{pqrs} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_q^\dagger \hat{a}_r \hat{a}_s + \hat{V}_{\text{eff}}, \quad (\text{S.1})$$

where \tilde{h}_{pq} are the effective one-electron integrals, defined as

$$\tilde{h}_{pq} = h_{pq} + \sum_i^{\text{core}} (g_{iqpi} - g_{iipq}), \quad (\text{S.2})$$

with h_{pq} denoting the one-electron integrals from the original Hamiltonian; and the effective potential term \hat{V}_{eff} , accounting for the core spin-orbitals, is given by

$$\hat{V}_{\text{eff}} = \sum_i^{\text{core}} h_{ii} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{ij}^{\text{core}} (g_{jii} - g_{jjii}). \quad (\text{S.3})$$

Note that indices i, j run over the core spin-orbitals, while p, q, r, s run over the active spin-orbitals.

S2 Compression of electronic Hamiltonians

In this section, we analyze the impact of Hamiltonian compression on the ground state energy. Additionally, we examine how the size of the Hamiltonian evolves as the number of active space orbitals increases, considering different compression thresholds. For this study, we construct the Hamiltonian for increasing active space sizes, ranging from 2 to 12 molecular orbitals, and apply different compression thresholds (1e-2, 1e-3, and 1e-4). The results are calculated using canonical orbitals (Figures S3 and S3), and using natural orbitals S1 and S2.

Focusing in natural orbitals, figure S1 (left) shows the number of Hamiltonian terms as a function of the active space size. As expected, the number of terms increases with the active space size. For small active spaces, there is almost no difference between the three compression thresholds. However, beyond 8 orbitals, a significant difference emerges between 1e-2 and the other two (1e-3 and 1e-4). In this regime, the number of terms is notably reduced for 1e-2, while for 1e-3 and 1e-4, the difference remains marginal.

Figure S1 (right) illustrates the impact of compression from an energy perspective by plotting the ground state (GS) energy as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms. The results indicate that a compressed Hamiltonian provides a better GS energy-to-terms ratio compared to the uncompressed Hamiltonian. This trend holds for all compression thresholds except 1e-2, where, around 1000 terms, the ratio deteriorates, leading to a GS energy higher than that of the uncompressed Hamiltonian for the same number of terms.

In Figure S2, we analyze the evolution of the GS energy error (defined as the difference between the GS energy of the compressed and uncompressed Hamiltonians) with respect to both the active space size (left) and the number of Hamiltonian terms (right). Even for a compression threshold of 1e-2, the GS energy error remains within chemical accuracy up to an active space of 6 orbitals. For 1e-3 compression, the GS energy remains below chemical accuracy up to 12 molecular orbitals. Notably, the difference between 1e-3 and 1e-4 is minimal.

Examining the energy error as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms, we observe that a 1e-3 compression is highly efficient up to 6 active orbitals, yielding a Hamiltonian with negligible loss relative to the uncompressed one. Beyond this point, the energy error increases exponentially with both the number of active orbitals and the number of Hamiltonian terms.

These results suggest that as the active space size increases—and thus the accuracy of the GS energy improves—small terms become more relevant, limiting the extent to which compression can be applied. However, for active spaces of up to 6 orbitals, a compression threshold of 1e-2 appears sufficient to maintain the GS energy error below chemical accuracy.

Figure S1: Analysis of the impact of Hamiltonian compression on the number of Hamiltonian terms and the ground state energy. On the left, we show the number of Hamiltonian terms as a function of the active space size for different Hamiltonian with three compression thresholds (1e-2, 1e-3, and 1e-4), compared to the uncompressed Hamiltonian. On the right, we plot the ground state (GS) energy as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms. The GS energies have been computed using the FCI method for three different compression thresholds (1e-3, 1e-4, and 1e-5). The Hamiltonian is expressed in the basis of natural Orbitals.

Figure S2: Analysis of the energy error with respect to different Hamiltonian compression thresholds ($1e-2$, $1e-3$, and $1e-4$). On the left, we show the ground state energy error as a function of the active space size. On the right, we present the GS energy error as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms. The ground state energy energies have been computed using the FCI method. The Hamiltonian is expressed in the basis of natural Orbitals.

Examining the results obtained using canonical orbitals (Figures S3 and S4), we observe that the use of canonical orbitals is detrimental compared to the use of natural orbitals. The energy-to-number-of-terms ratio presented in Figure S3 (right) is significantly worse than that observed with natural orbitals, where compression provides little to no benefit at any level. Furthermore, we observe that the GS energy error with respect to the uncompressed Hamiltonian (Figure S4) is substantially higher when using canonical orbitals, frequently exceeding chemical accuracy.

This suggests that the use of natural orbitals leads to Hamiltonians where the most important interactions are concentrated in a smaller number of terms, making the compression procedure more effective. However, it is important to note that as higher precision is required, the contribution of small Hamiltonian terms becomes more significant, and their impact on the ground state energy may no longer be negligible.

Figure S3: Analysis of the impact of Hamiltonian compression on the number of Hamiltonian terms and the ground state energy. On the left, we show the number of Hamiltonian terms as a function of the active space size for different Hamiltonian with three compression thresholds (1e-2, 1e-3, and 1e-4), compared to the uncompressed Hamiltonian. On the right, we plot the ground state (GS) energy as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms. The GS energies have been computed using the FCI method for three different compression thresholds (1e-3, 1e-4, and 1e-5). The Hamiltonian is expressed in the basis of canonical orbitals.

Figure S4: Analysis of the energy error with respect to different Hamiltonian compression thresholds (1e-2, 1e-3, and 1e-4). On the left, we show the ground state energy error as a function of the active space size. On the right, we present the GS energy error as a function of the number of Hamiltonian terms. The ground state energy energies have been computed using FCI method with a bond dimension of 200. The Hamiltonian is expressed in the basis of canonical Orbitals.

S3 Fermion vs. Qubit operator pools

The quantum circuits generated by fermionic ADAPT-VQE are constructed by mapping fermionic operators to qubit operators and implemented on quantum hardware using a first-order Trotter approximation. We note that this Trotterization can potentially break some

symmetries.

Figure S5: Ground state energy (in Hartrees) as a function of the number of iterations for the simulation of the benzene molecule with fermion (green) and qubit (blue) ADAPT-VQE algorithm.

Figure S6: Comparison of the computational cost of VQE algorithms using fermion vs qubit operators for benzene molecule. On the left there is a break down of the total (accumulated) number of CNOTs used for all circuits in the full simulation. We separate this number in energy evaluations and gradient evaluations. On the right there is an analysis of the circuit depths of the circuits used to evaluate the energy and the gradients. We show the maximum circuit depth and the average circuit depth.

Figure S7: Comparison of the circuit depth (of the circuit used to evaluate the energy) vs energy obtained from an ADAPT-VQE simulation (exact). On the left fermion-ADAPT-VQE, on the right qubit-ADAPT-VQE.

S4 Classical optimizer

Figure S8: Energy surface generated by the scan over the coefficients of a two operator qubit-ADAPT-VQE ansatz of H_4 molecule. Left figure shows the scan along coefficients 1 and 2 and right figure is the scan along coefficients 2 and 3

Figure S9: (a) Ground state energy and (b) energy evaluations of benzene molecule along the qubit-ADAPT iterations using COBYLA (green) and COBYLA-MOD (blue). Each point corresponds to the average of 30 simulations using 1000 shots. Default tolerance in standard COBYLA is 10^{-3} Hartrees.

Figure S10: (a) Ground state energy and (b) energy evaluations of benzene molecule along the qubit-ADAPT iterations using COBYLA (green) and COBYLA-MOD (blue). Each point corresponds to the average of 30 simulations using 5000 shots. Default tolerance in standard COBYLA is 10^{-3} Hartrees.

S4.1 Stretched H_4 model

To test the COBYLA-MOD with highly correlated system we have analyzed the linear H_4 molecule with bond distance of 2 Å computed with the STO-3G basis set. For this example we have also used Qiskit Aer simulator to compute the energy with 1000 shots. In figure S11 we show a comparison of a the average of 30 qubit-ADAPT-VQE simulations using both COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. In the left plot we show the energy as a function of each iteration step and on the right we plot the number of energy evaluations. For reference we include two exact simulation computed using Fermion operators and qubit operators.

In this example we observe a significant improvement in the convergence of the energy using COBYLA-MOD with respect to COBYLA, however they converge to a similar final energy value. Also we observe that for each iteration of the ADAPT-VQE algorithm the number of energy evaluations required for the optimization is lower using COBYLA-MOD. Looking at the error bars associates to the values presented in these figures we also observe that dispersion obtained with COBYLA-MOD is smaller dispersion than using COBYLA. This indicates that the results are more reliable using COBYLA-MOD. This can be observed in figure S12 where we compare the energy distribution of the final converged energy using both COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. In this figure we observe that the average energy using COBYLA is slightly smaller but the deviation of the energy distribution is much larger than COBYLA-MOD.

Figure S11: Molecule H₄, Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD using a value of 0.1 for rhobeg. Number of shots is 1000. Default tolerance is 1e-3 Ha.

Figure S12: Molecule H₄. Distribution of the energy of the converged ground state. Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. Number of shots is 1000. Default tolerance is 1e-3 Ha.

Figure S13: Molecule H_4 . Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. Fermion vs qubit operators using a value of 0.1 for rhobeg. Number of shots is 1000. Energy as a function of the iterations (left) and evaluations of the energy (right)

Figure S14: Molecule H_4 . Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. Fermion vs qubit operators using a value of 0.1 for rhobeg. Number of shots is 1000

Figure S15: Molecule H_4 . Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. Exact energy evaluation vs ADAPT iterations (left) and energy error with respect to FCI (right)

Figure S16: Molecule H_4 . Comparison of the optimization using COBYLA and COBYLA-MOD. Energy evaluations vs ADAPT iterations

S5 Circuit optimization

Table S1: Circuit depth of the ansatz used at each iteration step of the Qubit-ADAPT using the two different CNOT orientations and the one generated by our algorithm (Optimal). For each version we show also the depth of the transpiled circuit for IBM `torino` quantum computer (ISA depth).

# op.	Standard			Reverse			Optimal		
	depth	CNOT	ISA	depth	CNOT	ISA	depth	CNOT	ISA
0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
1	10	6	22	8	6	24	8	6	24
2	10	12	82	8	12	74	8	12	80
3	19	18	126	17	18	132	17	18	132
4	35	32	173	33	32	181	33	32	181
5	42	38	207	39	38	215	39	38	215
6	44	44	197	41	44	215	41	44	215
7	57	54	242	54	54	253	54	54	253

Table S2: Circuit depth of the ansatz used at each iteration step of the Fermion-ADAPT using the two different CNOT orientations and the one generated by our algorithm (Optimal). For each version we show also the depth of the transpiled circuit for IBM `torino` quantum computer (ISA depth).

# op.	Standard			Reverse			Optimal		
	depth	CNOT	ISA	depth	CNOT	ISA	depth	CNOT	ISA
0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
1	73	48	110	68	48	64	67	46	64
2	73	96	232	68	96	149	67	92	149
3	696	576	1244	683	576	1059	616	514	1060
4	1110	896	1949	1090	896	1631	979	794	1628
5	1182	944	2072	1157	944	1719	1045	840	1726
6	1254	992	2074	1157	992	1720	1045	886	1718
7	1408	1040	2183	1224	1040	2293	1111	932	1790

S6 Job Size Limitations in IBM Quantum Computers

To estimate the computational limitations of IBM quantum computers, we submitted a series of jobs using the `Estimator` primitive from the IBM Qiskit Runtime. These jobs varied in

both the number of two-qubit gates and the number of Pauli observables measured.

The data shown in the plot below reflects the limitations observed at the time of writing this manuscript. A job was considered not allowed if the server returned an error at submission time, indicating that the circuit exceeded current resource or policy constraints.

Figure S17: Maximum job size accepted by various IBM quantum computers, measured as the product of the number of two-qubit gates and the number of measured Pauli operators in the observable. IBM Brussels was tested 3 times

S7 Quantum hardware experiments

Figure S18: Energy evaluations (in Ha) with Qubit-ADAPT ansätze with 0-7 qubit operators measured in the IBM Torino computer using 9000 shots per sample. The coefficients of the ansatz are obtained from an exact calculation. Horizontal lines indicate the exact HF (green) and FCI with 4 active orbitals and 4 active electrons (gray). The energy difference between HF and FCI (correlation energy) is 53.9 mHa. Error bars corresponds to 2σ .

S8 Instruction execution times

Instructions times consider in our Qubit-ADAPT simulations with `Qiskit Aer` simulator are shown in Table S3, corresponding to:

- Parameterized single-qubit rotation gates
 - U1: phase shift gate.
 - U2: single-qubit rotation with two parameters.
 - U3: general single-qubit unitary rotation with three parameters.
- CX: CNOT gate.
- Reset: reset operation initializing a qubit back to the $|0\rangle$ state.
- Measure: the measurement operation collapses a qubit's state into either $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ and records the result.

Table S3: Instruction execution times (in ns) used in the noise model.

instruction	time
U1	0
U2	50
U3	100
CX	300
Reset	1000
Measure	1000